

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-120-IBN-5-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 120
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	260.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 260.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/15/2022 9:52:37 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:36:56 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.114	1807723	49.97	243061
2	6.444	1809613	50.03	225945

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-119-IBN-5-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 119
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	260.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 260.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/16/2022 9:29:53 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:37:42 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.988	113879	2.52	15490
2	6.293	4402386	97.48	564037